

INTERACTION OF NITROUS ACID AND METHYLAMINE : INFLUENCE OF THE ACIDITY OF THE MEDIUM

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Increasing acidity initially favours the amine-nitrous acid reaction; subsequently a critical point is reached any increase beyond which suppresses the reaction. The self decomposition of nitrous acid, which more or less always accompanies this change, also shows a similar initial augmentation, followed in this case by attainment of a maximum rate of decomposition. Comparison of the results with those obtained with ammonium chloride and thiocarbamide suggests that the mechanism of $-NH_2-HNO_2$ interaction is similar in all the three cases.

When nitrous acid interacts with carbamide (Werner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 863), thiocarbamide (Werner, *ibid.*, 1912, 101, 2180; Coade and Werner, *ibid.*, 1913, 103, 1221) and amides (Plimmer, *ibid.*, 1925, 2651; Sidgwick, Taylor and Baker, "The Organic Chemistry of Nitrogen", Oxford, 1942, reprint, pp. 23, 349), the acidity of the medium is a factor of prime importance. Little information, save the observations of Taylor (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 1099, 1897), is, however, available on the influence of this factor on the amine-nitrous acid reaction. The present investigation was therefore undertaken to extend these studies to a simple amine, like methylamine.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experiments were carried out with methylamine hydrochloride prepared by the methylation of ammonium chloride by formaldehyde (Werner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 844).

It was purified from dimethylamine and ammonium chloride by repeated crystallisation from alcohol and treatment with dry chloroform. The purity of the sample was confirmed by estimating the amine. A normal solution of this was used as the stock solution. As a source of nitrous acid, normal sodium nitrite solution, standardised by the thiourea method (cf. Coade and Werner, *loc. cit.*), was used.

Experiments were carried out in a Lunge's nitrometer using mg. molar quantities of the reactants. The reaction medium was the acid of the desired concentration. After mixing the reactants by gently shaking the nitrometer, the reaction was allowed to proceed for a fixed duration of time at the end of which the gas was measured and its composition determined (Werner, *loc. cit.*).

Attempts were made earlier to measure the velocity of this interaction by observing the rate of gas evolution (Arndt, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1901, 39, 64; 1903, 46, 570; Blanchard, *ibid.*, 1902, 41, 681; Euler, *Annalen*, 1903, 330, 280), but since nitric oxide formed by the decomposition of HNO_2 was invariably present and in certain cases (*vide infra*) formed the bulk of the evolved gas, these observations did not always give a correct picture of the amine-nitrous acid interaction. As, in the present case, known quantities of both the reactants have been used and the gaseous products also have been measured and analysed, the observations, it is felt, represent a reasonably

correct picture of the change. Other objections (Taylor, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 1099) to the procedure followed might be: (i) that unless the reactants are continuously and thoroughly agitated the rate of gas evolution cannot be an accurate measure of the velocity of the reaction, and (ii) such agitation greatly increases the rate of decomposition of nitrous acid. A third possible objection is the presence of solid particles (e.g. those of barium sulphate in Taylor's experiments) which also greatly increase the decomposition of nitrous acid.

As will be evident from the results shown in Table I, a comparison of the composition of the gas evolved (approximately at constant volume), when the nitrometer is vigorously shaken during the reaction time and when it is kept undisturbed after mixing the reactants, leaves little doubt that the reaction under both conditions follows substantially the same course, except that in the former case it is accelerated as a whole due to shaking. There is no evidence of a specially increased rate of nitrous acid decomposition.

TABLE I

Medium	Reaction mixture shaken during the expt.				Reaction mixture undisturbed during the expt.				
	Total gas (c.c.)*	Duration of experiments		Total gas (c.c.)	60 mins.		Total gas.	24 hours	
		% N ₂ .	% NO.		% N ₂ .	% NO.		% N ₂ .	% NO.
Acetic acid 6%	...	...	...	...	...	...	16.0	75.5	24.5
10	...	...	...	7.3	71.2	28.8	19.0	74.7	25.3
20	8.3	85.5	14.5	9.0	72.2	27.8	19.3	65.3	34.7
40	10.3	64.0	36.0	10.5	66.6	33.4	19.8	61.1	38.9
66	9.8	32.9	67.1	8.8	35.2	64.8	16.4	50.0	50.0
2N-H ₂ SO ₄	9.8	5.1	94.9	6.2	2.0	98.0	11.9	3.0	97.0

In the present experiments, there were no solid particles in the medium except in the case of reactions in sulphuric acid, where due to the action of nitrous acid on mercury a black powdery deposit (presumably, an oxide of mercury) was formed during the reaction. Under a uniform procedure of experimentation therefore the results are quite comparable.

The results with methylamine have been presented in Tables II-IV and in Figs. 1 and 2. Experiments were also carried out with ammonium chloride (Merck's A. R.) and thiocarbamide following similar procedure. A comparison of the typical results with methylamine and these substances has been shown in Table V and graphically in Fig. 3.

* These volumes are directly comparable because all the experiments were carried out between 22° and 25° and 758 and 759 mm. Hg.

Estimation of Methylamine

In experiments 1 and 10 of Table III, and those recorded in Table IV, the residual methylamine was estimated after the fixed period by distillation with NaOH. The method, on previous test, was found to give results accurate to $\pm 1\%$.

Interaction of Nitrous Acid and Methylamine: Influence of the Acid conc. of the Medium and other Factors.—The experiments were carried out in a Lunge's nitrometer with mg. molar quantities of reactants. Each experiment was allowed to proceed for a duration of one hour, at the end of which the volume of the gas evolved was noted and its composition determined. The progress of the reaction was followed by observing the volume of the evolved gas every ten minutes. By adopting a uniform procedure the results, on repeating the experiments, showed agreement within 5% (Table II).

TABLE II

Expt. No.	Reactants.	Medium.	Dilution.	Gas evolved during						Total gas at N.T.P.	Composition of the gas (c.c.)		Remarks.
				10 min. (c.c.)	20 min. (c.c.)	30 min. (c.c.)	40 min. (c.c.)	50 min. (c.c.)	60 min. (c.c.)		%N.	%NO.	
	2	3	4	5						6	7	8	9
1	Me NH ₂ .HCl and HNO ₂ in 1:1 ratio	6% Acetic acid.	5 c.c.	0.9	1.3	2.6	3.6	4.2	4.9				
2	"	10%	"	1.8	3.4	4.7	5.7	6.5	7.3	6.45 c.c.	71.2 (5.2)	28.8 (2.1)	
3	2:1	"	"	2.0	3.8	5.0	6.3	7.5	8.6		87.2 (7.5)	12.8 (1.1)	
4	1:1	"	11	0.4	0.6	0.9	1.2	1.6	1.9				
5	"	"	5	0.5	1.1	1.8	2.6	3.4	4.1	...	...		Mercury of the nitrometer was covered with CCl ₄ .
6	"	20%	"	1.9	4.0	5.9	7.0	8.1	9.0	7.95	72.2 (6.5)	27.8 (2.5)	
7	"	40%	"	3.2	5.0	7.0	8.4	9.5	10.5	9.3	66.6 (7.0)	33.4 (3.5)	
8	HNO ₂ only	"	"	2.9	1.4	1.9	2.3	2.7	3.1		0.0 (0.0)	100 (3.1)	
9	As in Expt. 1.	50%	6	4.0	6.2	7.8	8.8	9.6	10.3	9.12	44.6 (4.6)	55.4 (5.7)	
10	"	66%	7.5	3.4	5.0	6.5		8.0	8.8	7.92	35.2 (3.1)	64.8 (5.7)	The decrease in the reaction velocity might be due to dilution.
11	"	2N.H ₂ SO ₄	5	3.4	3.8	4.5	5.2	5.7	6.2	5.6	2.0 (0.1)	98.0 (6.1)	

(Vide Figs. 1 and 2.)

Interaction of Nitrous Acid and Methylamine: Influence of Acid conc. and other Factors.—The experiments were carried out in a Lunge's nitrometer with mg. molar quantities of reactants. Each experiment was allowed to proceed for 24 hours, at the end of which the gas evolved was measured and its composition determined (Table III).

TABLE III

Expt. No.	Reactants.	Medium.	Dilution.	Gas evolved at		Comp. of the gas.		Remarks.
				room temp.	NTP.	% N ₂ (c.c.)	% NO (c.c.)	
	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	Me.NH ₂ , HCl and HNO ₃ in 1 : 1 ratio.	6% Acetic acid.	5 c.c.	18.0 c.c.	15.98 c.c.	75.5 (13.6)	24.5 (4.4)	On estimation of methylamine in the reaction mixture (in a separate experiment) 23% were found unused.
2	"	"	"	21.2	—	79.2 (16.8)	20.8 (4.4)	The experiment was allowed 72 hours.
3	"	10% "	"	19.0	16.87	74.7 (14.2)	25.3 (4.8)	
4	"	"	"	17.5	—	83.4 (14.6)	16.6 (2.9)	The mercury was covered by a column of CCl ₄ .
5	"	"	11 c.c.	13.6	—	59.4 (8.7)	40.5 (5.5)	
6	"	20% "	5 c.c.	19.3	17.14	65.3 (12.6)	34.7 (6.7)	
7	"	40% "	"	19.8	17.58	61.1 (12.1)	38.9 (7.7)	
8	HNO ₃ only	"	"	11.5	—	0.0 (0.0)	100.0 (11.5)	(i) The reaction was allowed only 16 hours.
9	As in Expt. 1	66% "	"	16.4	14.56	50.0 (8.2)	50.0 (8.2)	(ii) On estimation of amine at the close of expt. (in a separate expt.) all the amine was found unreacted.
10	"	2N-H ₂ SO ₄	"	11.9	10.56	3.0 (0.35)	7.09 (10.55)	
11	"	"	"	7.9	—	10.1 (0.8)	89.9 (7.1)	The mercury was covered by a column of CCl ₄ .

Interaction of Nitrous Acid and Methylamine : Influence of Acid Concentration.*—The experiments were carried out with mg. molar quantities of the reactants. These were left mixed up in test tubes for a period of 24 hours at the end of which the residual methylamine in these was estimated (Table IV)**.

TABLE IV

Expt. No.	Reactants.	Medium.	Dilution.	Methylamine decomposed (%)	
				5	5
	2	3	4		
1	Me. NH ₂ , HCl and HNO ₃ in 1 : 1 ratio.	Acetic acid	5 c.c.	(i)	44.0
		6%		(ii)	42.0
2	"	10 "	"	(i)	40.0
		"	"	(ii)	38.0
3	"	20 "	"	(i)	36.0
		"	"	(ii)	35.0
4	"	40 "	"	(i)	26.0
		"	"	(ii)	26.0
5	"	66 "	"	(i)	20.0
		"	"	(ii)	21.0
6	"	2N-H ₂ SO ₄	"	(i)	2.0
		"	"	(ii)	4.0

* Vide Fig. 3.

** In a couple of experiments, separately carried out using larger quantities of the reactants (10 mg. moles each), the contents were tested for the presence of formaldehyde, formic acid and sym-dimethylhydrazine as possible oxidation products of methyl alcohol or methylamine, but none was detected.

*Interaction of Nitrous Acid with Methylamine, Ammonium Chloride and Thiocarbamide.**—Influence of the acid concentration of the medium on the progress of the reaction as indicated by the proportion of nitrogen in the evolved gases is shown below.

TABLE V

Medium.	% N ₂ **from NH ₄ Cl.	% N ₂ from MeNH ₂ ,HCl	% N ₂ from thiocarbamide.	% Methylamine decomposed. (in test tubes)
1	2	3	4	5
6% Acetic acid.	77.7	75.5	82.4	83.0
10 „ „		74.7	84.7	39.0
20 „ „	60.8	65.3	79.6	35.5
40 „ „	50.7	61.1	77.3	26.0
66 „ „	46.4	50.0	68.1†	20.5
2N-H ₂ SO ₄	15.8	3.0	3.5	3.0

(Vide Fig. 3, curves 1, 2 and 3).

* Experiments with methylamine hydrochloride, and ammonium chloride were allowed to proceed for 24 hours (and were yet incomplete), but those with thiocarbamide were complete within a few minutes.

** Only percentages of N₂ are shown, the rest of the gas was nitric oxide.

† In the case of thiocarbamide the medium contained 80% acetic acid.

DISCUSSION

Mainly two reactions appear to be taking place in the nitrometer :

(i) The amine-nitrous acid interaction according to the equation

(ii) The spontaneous or self decomposition of nitrous acid, presumably, according to some such process as $3\text{HNO}_2 \rightarrow \text{HNO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + 2\text{NO}$.

The progress of (i) is indicated by the amount of nitrogen formed, and of (ii) by that of nitric oxide. That the nitrogen is exclusively a product of (i) is well indicated by the results of Expts. 1 and 10 (Table III, column 9).

As judged by the composition and quantities of gas evolved (vide Tables I-III), interaction of methylamine and nitrous acid is incomplete even after 24 hours. The reaction is very much faster in the initial stages as indeed is to be anticipated owing to the larger concentration of the reactants then available. A comparison of the results in Tables II and III (column 6) indicates that almost 50% of the total reaction undergone in 24 hours, is complete within first 60 minutes of starting the reaction. It is clear therefore that any conclusions with respect to the influence of the factor under consideration would be nearer the truth, if they are drawn from the progress of the reaction in the first hour of the change (vide Table II).

The influence of acid concentration on (i) the amine-HNO₂ interaction, (ii) the self

decomposition of nitrous acid, and (iii) the overall change comprising (i) and (ii), is illustrated by the volumes of nitrogen, nitric oxide, and the total gas evolved, shown in columns 7, 8 and 5-6 respectively of Table II (also vide Table III). It will be seen that the (i) is favoured by the increasing acid concentration up to a critical value, any increase beyond which affects the reaction velocity adversely and may even completely suppress the reaction. The change (ii) also shows at first a rapid and then a more gradual increase in the reaction rate; beyond a certain critical concentration of the acid, this change appears to indicate a sort of saturation effect in its velocity. The overall reaction velocity, as is to be expected on the basis of the individual trends of (i) and (ii), shows an increase at first and then a continuous and gradual decline. These results are graphically represented in Figs. 1 and 2.

FIG. 1

Interaction of HNO₂ with methylamine
(Vide Table II)

Curve 1-7—*influence of acid conc.*

Curves 2' 2'', 2'''—*influence of other factors on the velocity of the changes*

FIG. 2

Interaction of nitrous acid & methyl amine.

(Vide Table II)

The above observations are in agreement with the earlier findings (Adamson and Kenner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 838 ; Taylor, *ibid.*, 1928, 1099 ; Krall, *this Journal*, 1939, 16, 9) : (a) That a certain amount of free acid is essential for the occurrence of amine-nitrous acid interaction which is suppressed by the presence of excessive mineral acid and (b) that the self decomposition of nitrous acid is favoured in a strongly acidic medium. With respect to the latter change, the tendency at high acid concentrations towards a saturation effect in its velocity, as evinced by curve 2 of Fig. 2, is, indeed, remarkable and does not appear to have been noted earlier.

The occurrence of a critical acid concentration (p_H) for the optimum amine-nitrous acid interaction (for a given set of conditions) recalls of a similar phenomenon in the hydrolysis of amides which has been attributed to the formation of the salt of the amide in presence of a large excess of acid, the salt being incapable of hydrolysis (Sidgwick, Taylor and Baker, "The Organic Chemistry of Nitrogen" Oxford, 1942, p. 145). Further, it has been clear from the chemistry of

numerous amino compounds that a positively charged amino group behaves differently from an uncharged or weakly charged amino group (Sidgwick, Taylor and Baker, *loc. cit.*, pp. 62, 69, 135, 256, 391). The markedly differential behaviour of nitrous acid towards the amine in weak and strong acid media, observed in the present experiments, no doubt, arises due to the strong or weak polarity developed by the amino group under the respective conditions. It is not unlikely that much of the apparent complexity of the interaction of amino compounds with nitrous acid, in general, might be due to an inadequate recognition of this influence of hydrogen-ion concentration of the medium.

The mercury of the nitrometer has a catalysing influence on both the changes (vide Fig. 3, curves 4 and 5, and Expt. Nos. 2 and 5 of Table II, and Expt. Nos. 3 and 4, and 10 and 11 of Table III). The influence of dilution and of amine concentration is as expected; the former slows down the reaction while the latter speeds it up (vide Expt. Nos. 2-3, and 2-4 of Table II).

FIG. 3

Interaction of HNO₂ with thiocarbamide, methylamine and NH₄Cl

For curves 1-3, vide Table V.

" 4 " " IV

5—figures calc. from Table III.

The results with ammonium chloride and thiocarbamide show a general similarity with those with amine (vide Table V; Fig. 3, curves 1, 2 and 3). But in the case of thiocarbamide the reaction is characterised by the fact that it is very rapid as compared to that with NH₄Cl and CH₃NH₂. HCl and is completed within half

an hour. Secondly, the nitric oxide evolved in this case is not due to the self decomposition of HNO_2 , but is formed by a specific oxidation reaction of the thiocarbamide (Werner, *loc. cit.*, 1912). The reaction velocities of these three compounds with nitrous acid can be roughly represented in the order :

Thiocarbamide > methylamine > ammonium chloride (vide Fig. 3, curves 1, 2 and 3; cf. Taylor).

On the above results therefore it is suggested that the suppression of the $\text{NH}_2\text{—HNO}_2$ reaction at high acid concentrations (low p_a of the media) in the case of the amines, and its diversion through other channels in the case of thiocarbamide arises from the same cause viz., locking up of the amino group by salt formation.

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